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EFFECTIVENESS OF SELECTED TEACHING STRATEGIES IN MULTIGRADE CLASSES

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Abstract: The study focused on the effectiveness of selected teaching strategies in multigrade classes. This study was conducted at Aguho Elementary School during the school year 2012-2013, which is one of the multigrade schools in the district of Tanay II, Division of Rizal. Employing a combination of experimental and descriptive-evaluative methods, the research utilized self-directed learning, group learning, and peer teaching strategies in teaching Mathematics competencies. Mean and standard deviation were used to analyze the scores of control and experimental groups in pretests and posttests, while a dependent t-test determined the significant differences in their performance before and after exposure to the strategies. Findings revealed that the experimental group outperformed the control group, indicating a significant difference in the learning outcomes. Specifically, peer teaching was identified as the most effective strategy in teaching "Comprehension of Calendar," while group learning proved most effective for "Comprehension of Time." The results confirm that employing varied teaching strategies enhances learners' performance in multigrade settings, suggesting that aligning strategies to specific competencies can improve teaching and learning effectiveness in Mathematics.

Keywords: *Selected Teaching Strategies, Mathematics Competencies, Multigrade Classes*

Introduction

A multigrade class is defined as a classroom composed of two or more grade levels handled by a single teacher within a complete or incomplete elementary school. In this setting, children from different ages and varying abilities are taught together throughout the school year. While one teacher assumes the primary responsibility for instruction, additional support may come from parents and community members, depending on the teacher's ability to mobilize their involvement. Teaching in multigrade classes presents unique challenges, particularly in addressing the diverse learning needs of pupils. Learners often struggle with certain mathematical concepts due to differences in readiness, prior knowledge, and cognitive abilities. To address these challenges, the use of appropriate teaching strategies becomes crucial. The utilization of selected approaches—such as self-directed learning, group learning, and peer teaching—can greatly assist pupils in overcoming difficulties and in gaining a deeper understanding of mathematical concepts. These strategies not only enhance comprehension but also promote collaboration, independence, and active participation in the learning process, thereby improving overall academic performance in a multigrade classroom.

Scope and Limitations of the Study

This study focused on examining the effectiveness of selected teaching strategies in multigrade classes at Aguho Elementary School, District of Tanay II, Division of Rizal. The multigrade class, consisting of Grades One and Two, was divided into two groups through random sampling. Each group consisted of thirteen (13) pupils. The first group, designated as the control group, was composed of eleven (11) Grade One pupils and two (2) Grade Two pupils and was taught using the traditional lecture method. The second group, designated as the experimental group, was likewise composed

of eleven (11) Grade One pupils and two (2) Grade Two pupils and was exposed to the three selected teaching strategies: self-directed learning, group learning, and peer teaching. Both groups were given a pretest prior to the intervention and a posttest after the intervention to measure their performance. The lessons used for both groups were taken from the Mathematics competencies prescribed in the Basic Education Curriculum (BEC) for the fourth grading period. Specifically, the study was limited to the following competencies: (1) comprehension of calendar, (2) comprehension of time, and (3) comprehension of linear measurement. These topics were selected since they were the required competencies to be taught during the last quarter of the school year. To measure the effectiveness of the strategies, the researcher prepared a 20-item teacher-made test covering the three competencies, which was validated by Mathematics experts. The test served as both the pretest and posttest instrument administered to the respondents. The findings of the study, therefore, are limited to the scope of the fourth grading period competencies in Mathematics and to the specific group of Grade One and Grade Two pupils who participated in the research.

Statement of the Problem

This study aimed to determine the effectiveness of selected teaching strategies in enhancing the performance of pupils in multigrade classes in Aguho Elementary School, District of Tanay, Division of Rizal. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

Specifically, it sought answers to the following problems:

1. What is the level of performance of the control and experimental group as revealed by the pretest and posttest scores in terms of different teaching strategies in terms of the different competencies?
2. Is there significant difference on the level of performance of the respondents in the control group and experimental group as revealed by the pretest and posttest scores with respect to Comprehension of Calendar; Comprehension of Time and Comprehension of Linear Measurement?
3. What is the level of effectiveness of selected strategies in teaching multigrade classes?
4. Which among the selected strategies is the most effective in teaching mathematics in multigrade classes?

Assumption

The study assumed that the study aimed to determine the effectiveness of the selected teaching strategies in multigrade classes, descriptive and experimental were applied. The pretest and posttest experimental design made use of two groups which was the experimental and the control group exposed to the traditional method. The design involved the comparison of students that were exposed in using selected teaching strategies and those that were not exposed in using selected strategies. The descriptive method of research was used to analyze the effectiveness of the different strategies used in this study and to determine the student's perception regarding the use of self-directed learning, group learning and peer teaching.

Theoretical Framework

The study was anchored from the Ausubel's Meaningful Reception Theory. Ausubel's Meaningful Reception Theory proposed that learning is based upon the kind of super ordinate, presentational, and combinational processes that occur during the reception of information. A primary process in learning is subsumption in which new material is related to relevant

ideas in the existing cognitive structure on a non-verbatim basis. Meaningful results when new information is acquired by linking the new information in the learner's own cognitive structure. Ausubel believes that learning of new knowledge relies on what is already known. That is, construction of knowledge begins with observation and recognition of events and objects through concepts already possessed. Students learn by constructing a network of concepts and adding to them. Ausubel also stresses the importance of reception rather than discovery learning, and meaningful rather than rote learning. He declares that his theory applies only to reception learning in school settings. He didn't say, however, that discovery learning doesn't work; but rather that it was not efficient. In other words, Ausubel believed that understanding concepts, principles, and ideas are achieved through deductive reasoning.

Methods of Research Used

Since the study aimed to determine the effectiveness of the selected teaching strategies in multigrade classes, descriptive and experimental were applied. The pretest and posttest experimental design made use of two groups which was the experimental and the control group exposed to the traditional method. The design involved the comparison of students that were exposed in using selected teaching strategies and those that were not exposed in using selected strategies. The descriptive method of research was used to analyze the effectiveness of the different strategies used in this study and to determine the student's perception regarding the use of self-directed learning, group learning and peer teaching.

Statistical Treatment

The following statistical tools will be used in answering the problems. To determine the level of performance of the control and experimental group as revealed by the pretest and posttest scores, mean was used. To determine the significant difference on the level of performance of the control group and experimental group as revealed by the pre-test and post-test scores, t- test was used. To determine the level of effectiveness of the selected strategies in teaching multigrade classes such as independent learning, group learning and peer teaching, mean gain percentage was used. To determine which among the strategies is the most effective in teaching Mathematics in multigrade classes, qualitative discussion and analysis was employed.

Summary of Findings

Based on the results of the study, the following are the findings;

1. Level of Performance of the Control and Experimental Group as revealed by the Pretest and Posttest Scores in terms of Different Competencies with respect to Independent Learning, Group Learning and Peer Teaching
 - 1.1 With regards to the performance of the control group in the "Comprehension of Calendar", "Comprehension of Time" and "Comprehension of Linear Measurement", the mean results in the pre- test and post-test are are low-average; low-high; and average-high respectively;
 - 1.2 While the experimental group marked average-high and high-very high verbal interpretation.

2. Performance of the Respondents in the Control Group and Experimental Group as Revealed in the Pre-test and Post-test Results with respect to the Different Learning Competencies in Mathematics.

2.1. There is no significant difference on the performance of the respondents in the control group with respect to different Learning Competencies in Mathematics as revealed in the pretest and posttest results.

2.2. The posttest mean scores of the experimental group is significantly higher than their pre-test means scores.

3. Level of Effectiveness of Selected Strategies in Teaching Mathematics for Multigrade Classes.

Group Learning marked a mean gain of 2.46 with gain relative percentage of 65.25 in teaching Comprehension of Time. Similarly, Peer Teaching obtained a mean gain of 1.77 and 67.56 gain relative percentage in teaching "Comprehension of Calendar". Both interpreted as "Much Effective". However, Self-directed learning marked a mean gain of 1.46 and gain relative percentage of 32.16 and verbally interpreted as "Less Effective".

4. Most Effective Selected Strategies in Teaching Mathematics in Multigrade Classes

Peer Teaching is the most effective strategy in teaching "Comprehension of Calendar" while Group Learning is the most effective strategy in teaching "Comprehension of Time."

Conclusion

From the findings of the study, the following conclusions were formulated:

1. On the performance of both the control and experimental group as regards their pretest and posttest, both posted improvement in result while no bearing was found and causal when it comes to experimental group.

Recommendations

On the basis of the summary of findings and the conclusions drawn, the following recommendations are hereby proposed:

1. Utilize strategies like peer teaching in teaching the "Comprehension of Calendar" and group learning in the teaching of "Comprehension of Time".
2. Expose pupils to different enrichment activities using varied teaching strategies to arouse student's interests thereby improving performance.
3. Parallel study should be done along the line using other variables like online modalities in teaching Mathematics.

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